

A literature review on the effect of extracellular vesicles on chronic obstructive pulmonary disease

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Abstract

Background and Objective

Chronic obstructive pulmonary disease (COPD) is a leading cause of morbidity and mortality worldwide. Current therapies offer only symptomatic relief, underscoring the need for novel diagnostic and therapeutic strategies. Extracellular vesicles (EVs), including exosomes and microvesicles, have emerged as promising candidates for biomarkers, intercellular signaling mediators, and therapeutic tools. This review evaluates recent evidence on the role of EVs in COPD.

Methods

A structured search of PubMed and Google Scholar was conducted for studies published between 2015 and 2024 using terms including “extracellular vesicles,” “exosomes,” “microvesicles,” “COPD,” and “biomarkers.” Reviews, meta-analyses, and experimental studies were included, while pilot and observational studies were excluded. Findings were synthesized across three thematic domains: biomarkers, intercellular communication, and therapeutic applications.

Results

EVs carry bioactive cargo such as microRNAs, proteins, and lipids that mirror disease state and influence recipient cell behavior. EV-derived miRNAs (e.g., miR-223-3p, miR-374b-5p) differentiate COPD severity and exacerbations, while fibulin-3 has been identified as a novel proteomic biomarker. EVs also mediate disease mechanisms, with cigarette smoke-induced cargo promoting airway remodeling and inflammation. Preclinical evidence highlights therapeutic promise from mesenchymal stem cell-derived EVs (e.g., Exo-d-MAPPS) and adipose-derived nanovesicles, which improve lung function and reduce inflammation.

Conclusion

EVs represent a promising frontier in COPD research with potential as non-invasive

biomarkers and innovative therapeutics. However, challenges remain in standardizing isolation methods, validating reproducibility, and conducting large-scale clinical trials before clinical translation can be achieved.

Keywords

Extracellular vesicles; COPD; biomarkers; intercellular communication; targeted therapy; (MISEV)

Introduction

Chronic Obstructive Pulmonary Disease (COPD) is a chronic inflammatory lung disease that obstructs airflow from the lungs, and results in respiratory distress. COPD encompasses a spectrum of progressive pulmonary conditions which include emphysema, refractory asthma, and chronic bronchitis. According to the WHO, COPD will rank as the third most prevalent cause of mortality by 2030 worldwide (1). Formerly, COPD showed a markedly higher prevalence among males; nevertheless, recent studies indicate an incremental equilibration in incidence rates between the two genders. General clinical presentations of COPD include a productive cough, and dyspnoea. Advanced stages of the disease also exhibit cyanosis, tachycardia, tachypnoea (1),(3).

COPD is predominantly caused by smoking and prolonged exposure to irritants. Moreover, some of endogenous risk factors for the development of COPD involve genetic predisposition like alpha 1 anti-trypsin deficiency, along with history of tuberculosis and recurrent pulmonary infections (2). The pathogenesis of COPD includes inflammatory process of the lung parenchyma along with tissue destruction. Participating cells like neutrophils, t-lymphocytes, and macrophages are recruited in response to noxious stimuli such as cigarette smoke; resulting in the secretion of different types of cytokines and extracellular vesicles that contribute to the inflammation observed in COPD (3).

Complications arising from COPD can lead to pulmonary hypertension and respiratory failure; the most significant complication is an acute exacerbation of COPD (4),(5). Therapeutic interventions primarily consist of bronchodilators “short-acting/long-acting varieties”, inhaled corticosteroids, and antibiotics to treat the associated infection (6), (7). In the case of advanced disease, non-invasive ventilation alongside supplemental oxygen may prove advantageous (6).

What are Extracellular vesicles?

EVs are vesicles encapsulated by lipid membranes and secreted by a huge array of cellular entities. The components of EVs, often referred to as 'cargo', contain a range of biomolecules such as nucleic acids, proteins, and lipids. EVs are essential to the processes of intercellular communication and play a critical role in the pathogenesis of diseases (8). EVs mediate the transfer of their cargo to the recipient cells; thus, altering their behavior and state. Additionally, they are involved in the facilitation of metastasis and oncogenic processes. They can also aid in the propagation of pathologic proteins in neurodegenerative diseases (8),(9).

The principal subclasses of EVs involve exosomes “ also known as intraluminal vesicles”, which are particles originating from endosomes, and microvesicles (MVs) which are derived from the plasma membrane (9),(10). In the context of COPD, EVs have been the subject of research predominantly as potential biomarkers. The "Minimal Information for Studies of Extracellular Vesicles" (MISEV) guidelines summarize the complexities associated with the classification of extracellular vesicle subtypes based on biogenesis and origin (10). Additionally, MISEV provides three possible ways to classify EVs: by size, markers, and cellular origin.

Table 1 summarises the subcategories of EVs (9),(10),(11):

Table 1			
Extracellular vesicles class	Size in nm	Marker	The synthesis of EVs
Exosome	30-150 nm in diameter	ESCRT + their accessory proteins “Alix, TSG101, HSC70, and HSP90β”	Formed by the fusion of endosomes with the plasma membrane
Microvesicle	100-1000 nm	Cytosolic and plasma membrane proteins	Formed by direct outward budding of

			the plasma membrane
Apoptotic bodies	50-5000 nm	Proteins associated with cellular organelles such as Golgi apparatus and nucleus	Formed by cells that undergo apoptosis

The *aim* of this literature review is to examine the role of EVs in the pathogenesis and progression of COPD in response to stressors.

Methodology

This review is a comprehensive analysis of the existing literature aimed to better understand the impact of EVs on COPD. The methodology consists of two main stages: Data Gathering, and Data analysis and interpretation.

1. Data Gathering

In this part, the data is collected from “PUBMED”, the types of literature include scientific papers and reviews of other literature. The focus is on EVs and their effect on the pathogenesis and progression of COPD. The search terms and **keywords** included "extracellular vesicles," "EVs isolation", "exosomes", "microvesicles", "chronic obstructive pulmonary disease", "MISEV", "Apoptotic bodies", "prevalence of COPD", "EVs as biomarkers" "risk factors of COPD", "pathogenesis of COPD" and other related keywords. The time frame of included literature papers is from 2015 to 2024. Additionally, Inclusion criteria were meta-analysis, reviews, experimental studies , while exclusion criteria were pilot studies, and observational studies.

2. Data analysis and interpretation

In this part, we focused on extracting and analysing information from different reviews on the effect of EVs on COPD. Firstly, we looked at the scientific methods of isolating EVs; their advantages and limitations.

The biological specimens contain macromolecular complexes such as lipoproteins and protein aggregates which exhibit some biophysical features similar to those of extracellular vesicles. In the absence of preliminary segregation of EVs from these biological specimens,

there exists a substantial risk of misidentifying these contaminants as EVs during characterization process; consequently this can result in skewed scientific interpretations (11). EVs isolation is crucial as this allows for having a pure sample of EVs which can be used for further analysis of their contents and in biomarkers discovery. Table 2 summarises some of the methods used for EVs isolation.

Methods of EVs Isolation “Table 2” (11),(12)

Technique	Description	Advantages	Limitations
1- Differential ultracentrifugation	The separation of the particles is based on their density and sedimentation velocity.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> This technique is the most widely used due to its robustness and the ability to identify subpopulations when density gradient (DG) centrifugation is utilized 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Difficulty in attaining complete segregation of EVs The possibility of EVs rupture during the process due to high forces; however this can be resolved by using a density gradient of iodixanol or a cushion Large amount of starting material is needed
Size-exclusion chromatography “SEC”	The separation in SEC is based on the size of EVs. This technique involves the transit of a sample through a column packed with porous material; allowing larger particles to elute more rapidly than the smaller ones.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Characterised commercial kits are available which makes it better than differential ultracentrifugation Easy and fast 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Post isolation process is required because of the contamination with lipoprotein and albumin
Microfluidic system	The separation is based on electric, acoustic, magnetic properties, and immunoaffinity.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Efficient processing of small volumes Isolation and characterisation can be combined 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Reduced volume results in low yield

Precipitation	The separation is based on solubility. polyethylene glycol (PEG) possessing an average of 10 kilodaltons is used; which increases the hydrophobic interaction between EVs.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Cheap method and many commercial kits are available 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • There is a significant likelihood of co-isolating non-vesicular impurities which further requires post isolation decomplexation in order to purify the EVs
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Multifaceted "omics" encompasses a group of expansive and high-throughput methodologies for the analysis of the molecular components within EVs (13),(14). This analytical spectrum includes:

- 1- **Genomics**: to examine the DNA content of the EVs
- 2- **Proteomics**: to investigate the protein composition of EVs which can aid in understanding the physiological state of the origination cells; and in disease biomarkers.
- 3- **Lipidomics**: used for profiling the lipid components of EVs which is essential to EV's structure and function.
- 4- **Transcriptomics**: for the examination and analysis of the mRNA and miRNA

A holistic view of the potential roles of EVs and their molecular profile can be gained by applying the omics strategies. Thus, leading to the advancement of diagnostic and therapeutic strategies (14).

Result and analysis

A. EVs as Biomarkers

Biomarkers comprise clinical features that are indicative of disease activity and determine variability concomitant with the state of the disease. This characteristic makes them helpful for the purposes of diagnosis, the evaluation of therapeutic response, and the surveillance of disease progression. In the field of pulmonary research, blood and bronchoalveolar lavage fluid (BALF) constitute the principal specimens used for EV's examination; however blood is preferred due to its feasibility of access. A study investigated the miRNA content of EVs in different COPD severity stages. In this study 40 COPD participants were enrolled "20 of which during an exacerbating event". They used statistical analysis on the isolated EVs from the patient blood, and they discovered a dysregulation of five miRNA in exacerbating patients when compared to stable patients (15). It was shown that miR-223-3p exhibited the highest area under the curve AUC=0.755 which is one of the miRNAs that is dysregulated in exacerbating COPD patients. Moreover, they discovered that miR-374b-5p was significantly over-expressed in patients with very severe COPD, as classified by the GOLD staging system, compared to those with moderate COPD (15). This study provided evidence that the bioactive components of EVs; particularly miRNAs possess definitive biological information for different COPD stages and could serve as potential biomarker.

Another study was established for the discovery of novel COPD biomarkers using next-generation proteomics (16). The study determined several proteins that were significantly upregulated in COPD patients compared to healthy controls. One of these proteins is Fibulin-3 which was confirmed by immunoblotting of EVs and immunohistochemistry. Fibulin-3 maintains the structural integrity of the elastic fibres in the lung. The upregulation of Fibulin-3 is attributable to a compensatory reaction to the tissue damage associated with the disease. Moreover, the study demonstrated that mice deficient in fibulin-3 develop emphysema with advancing age, suggesting that this protein could be used to better understand the pathogenesis of COPD (16). This study showed that Fibulin-3 could act as a novel biomarker for COPD.

Further study looked into the presence of microvesicles within the bronchoalveolar lavage fluid of individuals who smoke, both with and without COPD and compared them to non-smokers (17). They discovered an increase in alveolar macrophage-derived MVs in COPD patients who smoke compared to non-smokers. It was determined that the increased AM-MV correlated with both the number of pack-years smoked and the severity of airway obstruction (17). This study suggests that AM-MVs may possess potential as biomarkers for the

progression of COPD and might provide insight into the underlying mechanisms of the disease.

Figure 1:

Conceptual overview of extracellular vesicles (EVs) in chronic obstructive pulmonary disease (COPD). Bronchial epithelial cells, macrophages, and neutrophils release EVs (represented as yellow circles) containing bioactive cargo such as microRNAs (e.g., miR-223-3p, miR-374b-5p), proteins (e.g., fibulin-3, neutrophil elastase), and lipids. These vesicles contribute to airway inflammation, airway remodeling, and immune modulation, thereby influencing COPD pathogenesis. Emerging evidence suggests that mesenchymal stem cell (MSC)-derived EVs and artificial nanovesicles may counteract these pathological processes by reducing inflammation and improving lung function. *(Created by the author.)*

B. EVs in Intercellular communication

There are several cells that produce EVs which contribute to the pathogenesis of COPD; some of which include bronchial epithelial cells. An invitro co-culture study was conducted to evaluate the effect of cigarette smoke on the upregulation of miRNA-210 in the bronchial epithelial cells (18). Both human bronchial epithelial cells and a model of lung fibroblast were used in this study. Furthermore, the upregulation of miRNA-210 is packed within EVs and then released; causing differentiation of lung fibroblasts into myofibroblast. The study demonstrated that miRNA-210 is responsible for silencing the gene ATG7 within fibroblasts; hence suppressing autophagy (18),(19). This study provided insight on the role of EVs as intercellular communicators; the behaviour of lung fibroblast is altered which contribute to the airway remodelling seen in COPD.

Another study looked into the effect of endothelial microparticles EMPs; which are EVs derived from primary pulmonary microvascular endothelial cells (20). The study determined that EMPs and their cargo particularly “ miRNA-126” may influence lung tissue inflammation seen in COPD. It was determined that over-expression of miRNA-126 could have an anti-inflammatory effect in COPD (20). Furthermore, the study may be useful in understanding the effect of EMPs on the inflammatory process observed in COPD. It may also provide a potential therapeutic strategy for the disease.

Further study looked into the effect of activated neutrophil derived exosomes “ CD63⁺/CD66b⁺” in the pathogenesis of COPD (21). These are small vesicles that contain an enzyme called neutrophil elastase on their surface. It was determined that this enzyme “NE” is responsible for extracellular matrix degradation in COPD patients. Also, NE is resistant to α 1-antitrypsin; making it difficult to be removed and more potent (21). This study identified a new potential mechanism of the underlying pathogenesis of COPD.

Figure 2: Role of EVs in COPD pathogenesis. Release of EVs from epithelial cells, macrophages, and neutrophils contributes to airway inflammation and remodeling, with potential as biomarkers and therapeutic agents. (Adapted from Wu et al., 2023 under CC BY 4.0 license). (25)

C. EVs as therapeutic tools

Conventional management of COPD predominantly involves the administration of corticosteroids and bronchodilators, which are essential in managing the disease's symptoms. However, emerging therapeutic strategies involving extracellular vesicles and stem cells represent a potential advancement in the treatment of this condition. A study was established to investigate the role of Mesenchymal stem cells -derived product called “Exo-d-MAPPS” in reducing the persistent airway inflammation of COPD patients (22). It was observed that Exo-d-MAPPS is rich in immune-regulating agents; this involves IL-1 receptor blockers, type I and II TNF receptors, and soluble receptors that neutralize advanced glycation end products. The study showed that after the administration of Exo-d-MAPPS, the respiratory function of the patients was significantly improved (22). Moreover, there was a reduction in serum level of inflammatory cytokines “IFN- γ , IL-12, and IL-1 β ” and an increase in the concentration of IL-10. Overall, it has been shown that Exo-d-MAPPS enhanced the respiratory function and life quality in COPD patients by playing a role in reducing the chronic inflammation. This study proposes that mesenchymal stem cells derived extracellular vesicles “Exo-d-MAPPS” may serve as a novel therapeutic tool for the treatment of COPD. Another study investigated the effect of IL-10 in the resolution of inflammation. The study demonstrated that a combination of steroid therapy and immunotherapy results in an increase of endogenous IL-10 which in turn inhibits eosinophilia and attenuate airway inflammation (23).

Further experiment that used mice model investigated the therapeutic benefits of introducing adipose stem cell “ASC”-derived nanovesicles in COPD (24). The study showed an increase of FGF2 level in the mice treated with the artificial nanovesicles. Moreover, the administration of a reduced dosage of artificial nanovesicles yielded a similar regeneration rate of lung epithelial cells in comparison to large quantities of naturally occurring ASC exosomes (24). This may serve as a novel strategy of using artificial vesicles for therapeutic purposes in COPD.

Additionally, EVs are utilized for drug delivery due to their stability and biocompatibility. Some of the methods to improve EV production and targeting may include chemical adjustment of EV surfaces, membrane fusion methods to increase yield and facilitate drug delivery, and genetic engineering (25). Inhaled drugs for COPD provide quick and direct effects with less systemic side effects but face challenges in dosage consistency and patient compliance. EV-based delivery systems could possibly offer the advantages of inhaled treatments while mitigating their limitations.

Discussion

Chronic Obstructive Pulmonary Disease “COPD” is a complicated and heterogeneous disease, marked by chronic airway inflammation, progressive destruction of lung tissue, and obstructed airflow due to structural changes within the airways. Exacerbations are considerably contribute to increased morbidity and mortality rates. Moreover, the lack of curative options emphasizes the critical need for novel diagnostics and therapeutic interventions in COPD.

Extracellular vehicles (EVs) have emerged as highly robust vectors of intercellular communication, capable of transferring a myriad of bioactive molecules to target cells, hence modulating and influencing a range of pathological and physiological processes in the recipient cells. Owing to their inherent stability and capacity to transport molecular cargo, extensive research has been initiated to investigate EVs as a potential novel therapeutic strategy (26). Recent studies have demonstrated the potential of EVs as biomarkers in COPD. They encapsulate specific proteins, lipids, and genetic material which mirror their originating cells. Therefore, EVs could provide a snapshot of the disease state, offering insights into the ongoing pathophysiological mechanisms. The deployment of EVs as biomarkers in COPD

could revolutionize disease surveillance, enabling highly precise and early identification of exacerbations or disease progression (26).

Furthermore, the prospect of designing synthetic EVs to deliver therapeutic compounds directly to the compromised lung tissues could herald a new era in COPD management. This approach could substantially mitigate systemic side effects and improve drug efficacy by ensuring localized delivery to the damaged tissues (27).

One of the main challenges that EVs encounter is the inherent heterogeneity, they exhibit considerable variation in size, function, and molecular composition. This heterogeneity hinders the establishment of standardized methods of isolation and characterization. However, MISEV guidelines help to standardize and enhance the reliability of EV studies, assuring that research is consistent and findings are comparable within the scientific domain. Clinically, the storage of EVs could be a problem as EVs content may leak over time due to temperature changes. Additionally, pharmacokinetics and biodistribution of EVs are also considered challenges in clinical settings (28).

Further investigation is warranted to explore the benefit of EVs in therapeutic intervention for the management of COPD and in the advancement of personalized medicine within the domain of respiratory diseases.

Limitations

This review has several limitations that should be acknowledged. The heterogeneity of extracellular vesicle (EV) isolation and characterization methods across studies introduces variability and complicates direct comparison of results. Much of the available evidence is based on preclinical investigations or small-scale clinical studies, which limits the overall strength of the conclusions that can be drawn. In addition, publication bias may have influenced the available literature, as studies with positive or novel findings are more likely to be reported. Finally, the absence of large, multicenter clinical trials restricts the generalizability and clinical translation of EV-based diagnostic and therapeutic approaches in chronic obstructive pulmonary disease (COPD). Addressing these limitations through standardized methodologies, robust study design, and clinical validation will be essential for advancing the field.

Conclusion

Chronic obstructive pulmonary disease (COPD) remains a major cause of morbidity and mortality worldwide, and current therapies primarily target symptom control rather than disease modification. Evidence demonstrates that extracellular vesicles (EVs) carry molecular cargo such as microRNAs, proteins, and lipids that mirror disease state and actively influence inflammatory pathways, immune regulation, and airway remodeling. Their capacity to serve as minimally invasive biomarkers has been highlighted in recent studies, with EV-derived miRNAs and proteins such as fibulin-3 showing diagnostic and prognostic potential.^(9,16) Preclinical work also suggests that mesenchymal stem cell–derived EVs and engineered vesicles hold promise as therapeutic agents capable of improving lung function and reducing inflammation.⁽²²⁾

Despite these advances, significant challenges remain before EVs can be integrated into clinical practice. Isolation methods lack standardization, EV heterogeneity complicates reproducibility, and the pharmacokinetics of EV-based therapies are still poorly understood. Addressing these gaps through large-scale clinical trials and harmonized methodological frameworks will be essential. Ultimately, EVs represent not only a window into COPD pathogenesis but also a potential platform for precision diagnostics and targeted therapy, with the capacity to transform future disease monitoring and management.

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Author Contributions

S.A. conceived the study, performed the literature search, analyzed and interpreted the findings, and drafted and revised the manuscript. The author has reviewed and approved the final version of the manuscript and is fully accountable for its content.

Conflicts of Interest

The author declares no conflicts of interest related to this work.

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Ethics Statement

This article is a literature review and does not contain any studies involving human participants or animals performed by the author.

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